

Facile total synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol, (\pm)-1,4-cuparenediol and (\pm)-cuparene-1,4-quinone[†]

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The total syntheses of the bicyclic sesquiterpene phenols (\pm)- α -herbertenol (**1**) and (\pm)-1,4-cuparenediol (**2**) have been successfully accomplished involving copper-catalysed conjugate addition of Grignard reagents to unsaturated dinitriles and α,α -dimethylation of primary esters as key reactions. Oxidation of **2** afforded the sesquiterpene quinone **3**.

Herbertane and cuparane sesquiterpenes possessing sterically crowded cyclopentane moieties have attracted considerable attention as synthetic targets in recent years, as some members exhibit interesting biological activities. α -Herbertenol (**1**), a sesquiterpene phenol of the herbertane family was isolated by Matsuo and coworkers¹ from the liverwort *Herberta adunca* along with several closely related phenols. Recently, Asakawa and coworkers reported² the isolation of the cuparane sesquiterpenes 1,4-cuparenediol (**2**) and cuparene-1,4-quinone (**3**) from Japanese liverworts.

Many of the sesquiterpenes isolated from liverworts, particularly the sesquiterpene phenols, show a wide spectrum of biological properties which include^{1,3} potent antifungal, neurotrophic and anti-lipid peroxidation activities. The total synthesis of naturally occurring herbertane and cuparane sesquiterpenes containing 1-ary1-1,2,2 trimethylcyclopentane ring system has been an active area of research in recent times and current interest⁴ in phenolic sesquiterpenes is reflected in a number of diverse synthetic approaches to these compounds. The synthesis of these sesquiterpenes is associated with the difficulty in the generation of two adjacent quaternary carbon atoms at C-1 and C-2 on a cyclopentane ring and an appropriately substituted, often highly substituted, aromatic ring at C-1. The first total synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol (**1**), which exhibits significant antifungal properties, was accomplished

by Fukuyama and coworkers³ using an intramolecular Heck reaction as a key step. Later, total synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol was reported by Eischer *et al.*⁵ and Harrowven *et al.*⁶ and enantioselective synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol was reported by Abad *et al.*⁷ and Fukuyama *et al.*⁸. Very recently, Srikrishna and coworkers⁴ achieved the synthesis of (\pm)-**1**, employing a ring-closing metathesis reaction based methodology. We envisaged that 1-tetralones which are easily accessible compounds would serve as useful starting materials for the generation of 1,1,2,2-tetra-substitutedcyclopentanes related to naturally occurring sesquiterpenes and we have now developed a facile and convenient general method for the synthesis of herbertane and cuparane sesquiterpenes from appropriately substituted 1-tetralones. Starting from the tetralones **4a** and **4b**⁹, we have successfully accomplished a new total synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol (**1**) and a facile total synthesis of (\pm)-1,4-cuparenediol (**2**) respectively, and our synthesis of the bioactive sesquiterpene phenols **1** and **2** is outlined in Scheme 1.

The tetralones **4a** and **4b**⁹ were condensed with malononitrile to provide the unsaturated dinitriles **5a** and **5b** in 94% and 95% yields, respectively. The first quaternary carbon atom was created through conjugate addition to the unsaturated dinitriles. Thus, conjugate addition of MeMgI to **5a** in the presence of CuI afforded **6a** (89%), which on hydrolysis, decarboxylation, and esterification furnished the methyl ester **7a** in 82% yield. The dinitrile **5b** was similarly converted into the methyl ester **7b** in 74% overall yield. The ester **7a** was converted in high yield into the corresponding α,α -dimethylated ester **9a** in a single step employing a sequential methylation of **7a**. Thus, alkylation of **7a** with MeI at -78° in the presence of LDA (1 equiv.)

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Scheme 1. 4a-13a : R¹ = H, R² = Me; 4b-13b : R¹ = Me, R² = OMe.

Reagents and conditions : (i) CH₂(CN)₂, NH₄OAc, AcOH, C₆H₆, reflux; (ii) MeMgI, CuI, Et₂O, THF, r.t. then reflux; (iii) KOH, HOCH₂CH₂OH, H₂O, reflux, then H₃O⁺, heat (190°); (iv) MeOH, H₂SO₄, reflux; (v) LDA (1 equiv.), THF, -20°; MeI, HMPA, -78°; (vi) LDA (1.7 equiv.), HMPA (2 equiv.), THF, 0°, MeI, 0–10°; (vii) CrO₃, AcOH-H₂O (4 : 1), 10°, r.t.; (viii) MCPBA, CH₂Cl₂, CF₃CO₂H, 0–25°; (ix) aq. KOH, MeOH, reflux, then Me₂SO₄, 50–80°, H₃O⁺; (x) CH₂N₂, Et₂O, 0°; (xi) t-BuOK, C₆H₆, reflux, H₃O⁺, DMSO, NaCl, 155°; (xii) N₂H₄, N₂H₄·2HCl, (HOCH₂CH₂)₂O, 125°; KOH, 210°; (xiii) BBr₃, CH₂Cl₂, 0°, r.t.; (xiv) (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆, MeCN, H₂O, 25°.

as the base yielded the monomethyl ester **8a** which without isolation was again alkylated with MeI in the presence of LDA (1.7 equiv.) and HMPA (2 equiv.) to give the desired α,α -dimethylated ester **9a** in 90% yield. α,α -Dimethylation of the ester **7b** was similarly carried out in a one-pot process to provide high yield of the ester **9b**. The second quaternary carbon atom was thus generated very efficiently and in an extremely facile manner, highlighting the potential of the present method. Oxidation of **9a** and **9b** with CrO₃ gave the keto-esters **10a** and **10b** in 75% and 78% yields respectively. Bayer-Villiger reaction of **10a** and **10b** with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in the presence of trifluoroacetic acid afforded the lactones **11a** and **11b** in 84% and 88% yields, respectively. Alkaline hydrolysis of **11a** followed by treatment with Me₂SO₄ and esterification with CH₂N₂ furnished the diester **12a** (85%). The lactone **11b** was similarly converted into the diester **12b** (85%). The spectral characteristics of the compounds **10-12** as revealed through their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were fully in accord with their structures.

Dieckmann cyclisation of diesters **12a** and **12b** in the presence of t-BuOK followed by decarbomethoxylation of the resulting crude β -ketoesters furnished the cyclopentanones **13a** and **13b** in 75% and 72% yields, respectively. Huang-Minlon reduction of **13a** followed by demethylation with BBr₃ afforded (\pm)- α -herbertenol (**1**) (72%) whose spectral data indicated the identity with natural product. Similarly, Huang-Minlon reduction of **13b** and subsequent demethylation of the resulting product with BBr₃ furnished (\pm)-1,4-cuparenediol (**2**) (71%). Oxidation of **2** with ceric ammonium nitrate afforded (\pm)-cuparene-1,4-quinone (**3**) in 88% yield. The identities of our synthetic compounds **2** and **3** were secured through comparison of ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR data with those of authentic compounds.

In conclusion, we have developed a convenient and useful general method for the synthesis of herbertane and cuparane sesquiterpenes using easily accessible 1-tetralones as the starting materials. A new total synthesis of (\pm)- α -herbertenol and facile total synthesis of (\pm)-1,4-cuparenediol

and (±)-cuparene-1,4-quinone have been achieved by the application of the present method.

Experimental

The compounds described and having asymmetric centres are all racemates. Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer model PE 298 and Shimadzu FTIR-8300 spectrophotometers. ^1H NMR (300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker DPX-300 spectrometer with SiMe_4 as internal standard. The chemical shifts (δ ppm) are reported relative to SiMe_4 (δ_{H} 0.00) for ^1H and the central line of residual CHCl_3 (δ_{C} 77.0) for ^{13}C . Moisture sensitive reactions were carried out using standard syringe-septum technique. Anhydrous solvents were obtained by standard procedures. All solvent extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Product purities were routinely checked by TLC. Ether refers to diethyl ether and light petroleum refers to the fraction of petroleum ether in the boiling point range 40° – 60° .

7-Methyl-1-tetralidinemalononitrile (**5a**) :

A mixture of commercially available 7-methyl-1-tetralone (**4a**) (10 g, 0.0625 mol), malononitrile (4.62 g, 0.07 mol), glacial acetic acid (4 ml), ammonium acetate (2 g) and dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 24 h with continuous removal of water [a Dean-Stark water separator was used]. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and washed successively with water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate, water again till neutral, and dried. The solid residue remaining upon evaporation of the solvent was crystallised from a mixture of ether and light petroleum to afford the unsaturated dinitrile (**5a**) (12.2 g, 94%) as light yellow needles, m.p. 93 – 94° (Found : C, 80.97; H, 6.04. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 80.74; H, 5.81%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2224 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.98 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.38 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.84, 3.00 (4H, 2t, J 6.3 Hz each, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 7.18 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz, ArH), 7.31 (1H, dd, J 7.8, 1 Hz, ArH), 8.02 (1H, bs, ArH); δ_{C} 20.9, 22.3, 29.2, 33.0, 79.3, 113.4, 114.0, 128.1, 129.3, 129.8, 134.6, 136.5, 139.0, 172.6.

6-Methyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralidinemalononitrile (**5b**) :

This was prepared from 6-methyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (**4b**) in 95% yield under the same reaction condition as above: m.p. 131 – 132° (Found : C, 75.70; H, 5.72. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 75.61; H, 5.92%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2210 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.98 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.26 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.79, 2.99 (4H, 2t, J 6.3 Hz each, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 3.88 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 7.04 (1H, s, ArH), 7.72 (1H, s, ArH); δ_{C} 16.6, 22.5, 29.0, 29.6, 33.1, 55.6, 108.2, 113.8, 114.7, 127.9, 131.4, 134.7, 134.8, 156.1, 172.3.

1-Dicyanomethyl-1,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (**6a**) :

Cuprous iodide (1 g, 0.005 mol) was added to a solution of the unsaturated dinitrile (**5a**) (6.25 g, 0.03 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (40 ml) at room temperature and the mixture was stirred for 10 min. A solution of methylmagnesium iodide [prepared from magnesium (1 g, 0.042 g atom) and methyl iodide (5.7 g, 0.04 mol)] in anhydrous ether (25 ml) was then added under nitrogen during 40 min with vigorous stirring. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 5 h and then heated under reflux for 1 h. It was then cooled in an ice bath, decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid (2 N, 40 ml) and extracted repeatedly with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and concentrated. The residue was evaporatively distilled at 170 – $172^\circ/0.2$ mm Hg to furnish the desired conjugate addition product **6a** (6 g, 89%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 80.11; H, 7.40; N, 12.39. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 80.32; H, 7.19; N, 12.49%); ν_{max} (film) 2260 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.58 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.75–2.23 (4H, m), 2.32 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.73–2.90 (2H, m), 4.05 (1H, s, $\text{CH}(\text{CN})_2$), 6.98–7.08 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$); δ_{C} 19.0, 21.1, 27.3, 29.3, 34.6, 35.9, 41.1, 112.0, 112.2, 126.2, 128.8, 129.9, 134.1, 136.2, 136.3.

1-Dicyanomethyl-1,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (**6b**) :

The compound **6b** was prepared from **5b** by the above procedure in 90% yield, m.p. 87 – 88° (Found : C, 75.50; H, 6.92; N, 10.87. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 75.56; H, 7.13; N, 11.01%); ν_{max} (KBr) $2250, 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$; δ_{H} 1.62 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.81–2.76 (6H, m), 2.16 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.82 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 4.01 (1H, s, $\text{CH}(\text{CN})_2$), 6.78 (1H, s, ArH), 6.89 (1H, s, ArH); δ_{C} 15.7, 19.0, 26.8, 28.7, 34.8, 35.8, 41.2, 55.4, 107.2, 112.0, 112.5, 126.9, 128.4, 131.9, 134.4, 156.3.

1-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-1,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (**7a**) :

The saturated dinitrile (**6a**) (5.6 g, 0.025 mol) was hydrolysed by heating under reflux for 25 h with a solution of potassium hydroxide (22.5 g) in ethylene glycol (75 ml) and water (15 ml). The mixture was cooled to room temperature, diluted with water (75 ml) and the neutral material was extracted with ether. The alkaline solution was then acidified with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with chloroform. The organic extract was washed with water, dried and concentrated. The crude product was decarboxylated by heating it at 190° for 20 min and the resulting acid (4.96 g) was esterified with dry methanol (50 ml) and concentrated sulfuric acid (2.5 ml) by heating

under reflux for 6 h. Usual work up afforded the methyl ester **7a** (4.75 g, 90%) as a colourless oil, b.p. 132–135°/0.6 mm Hg (Found : C, 77.62; H, 8.84. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires : C, 77.55; H, 8.68%); ν_{\max} (film) 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.57–2.06 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 2.29 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.54–2.75 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 3.60 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 6.83–6.93 (2H, m, ArH), 7.06 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 19.4, 21.2, 29.3, 30.0, 35.8, 36.3, 47.1, 51.1, 126.6, 126.9, 129.1, 133.2, 135.1, 143.4, 172.1.

1-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-1,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (7b) :

Following the procedure described above for **7a**, the ester **7b** was prepared from **6b** as a colourless oil in 82% yield, b.p. 160–162°/0.6 mm Hg (Found : C, 73.49; H, 8.62. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ requires : C, 73.25; H, 8.45%); ν_{\max} (film) 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.57–2.10 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 2.14 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.62–2.68 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 3.62 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 3.79 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 6.70 (1H, s, ArH), 6.81 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 15.6, 19.4, 29.3, 29.4, 35.8, 36.6, 41.1, 51.2, 55.4, 107.8, 124.5, 128.0, 131.3, 141.7, 155.9, 172.2.

Methyl 2-methyl-2-(1,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthyl)propanoate (9a) :

A solution of the ester (**7a**) (1.5 g, 6.46 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (4 ml) was added dropwise under nitrogen at -78° to a stirred solution of lithium diisopropylamide [prepared by adding 1.4 M *n*-butyllithium (4.7 ml, 6.58 mmol) in hexane to a stirred solution of diisopropylamine (0.69 g, 6.8 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (8 ml) at 0°]. After stirring the mixture at -20° for 2 h, methyl iodide (1.1 g, 7.75 mmol) in hexamethylphosphoramide (1.16 g, 6.48 mmol) was added dropwise at -78° and the resulting mixture was stirred at 0° for 2 h. It was then slowly added at 0° to a stirred solution of lithium diisopropylamide under nitrogen [prepared by adding 1.4 M *n*-butyllithium (7.8 ml, 10.92 mmol) in hexane to a solution of diisopropylamine (1.13 g, 11.2 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (4.5 ml) and hexamethylphosphoramide (2.3 g, 12.85 mmol) at 0°]. After stirring the mixture at 0° for 2 h, methyl iodide (4.6 g, 32.4 mmol) was slowly added and the resulting mixture was further stirred at $0-10^\circ$ for 2 h. It was then diluted with cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed thoroughly with water, dried and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with ether-light petroleum (1 : 3) furnished the α,α -dimethyl ester (**9a**) (1.5 g, 90%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 78.32; H, 9.20. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires : C, 78.42; H, 9.29%); ν_{\max} (film) 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.01 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.49 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.17–1.92 (4H, m), 2.28 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.45–2.72 (2H,

m), 3.62 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 6.95–7.05 (2H, m, ArH), 7.13 (1H, bs, ArH); δ_C ($CDCl_3$, 50 MHz) 21.0, 21.3, 22.3, 22.6, 26.3, 31.2, 35.4, 42.7, 50.3, 51.3, 126.4, 128.7, 128.8, 134.3, 136.1, 141.8, 178.0.

Methyl 2-methyl-2-(1,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthyl)propanoate (9b) :

α,α -Dimethylation of the ester **7b**, as described above for **9a**, furnished the ester **9b** as a colourless oil in 89% yield, b.p. 158–160°/0.4 mm Hg (Found : C, 74.59; H, 9.20. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3$ requires : C, 74.45; H, 9.02%); ν_{\max} (film) 1730 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.01 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.25 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.49 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.46–1.88 (4H, m), 2.15 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.52–2.56 (2H, m), 3.66 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 3.77 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 6.71 (1H, s, ArH), 6.79 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 15.6, 21.1, 22.5, 22.7, 26.4, 30.6, 35.2, 42.9, 50.3, 51.4, 55.3, 110.1, 124.1, 130.8, 130.9, 140.2, 155.4, 178.1.

4,6-Dimethyl-4-(1-methyl-1-methoxycarbonyl)ethyl-1-tetralone (10a) :

A solution of chromium trioxide (1.4 g) in 1.4 ml of water and 5.6 ml of glacial acetic acid was added slowly with stirring at 10° to a solution of the aforementioned ester (**9a**) (1.5 g, 5.77 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h and then diluted with water (50 ml) and extracted with ether (3×60 ml). The combined ethereal extract was washed with water, 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide till alkaline and with water again until neutral. The solvent was dried and evaporated off. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel (40 g). The solid fractions eluted with ether-light petroleum (1 : 4) were crystallized from a mixture of ether and light petroleum to afford the keto-ester (**10a**) (1.19 g, 75%) as colourless plates, m.p. 76–77° (Found : C, 74.68; H, 8.15. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires : C, 74.42; H, 8.08%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1722, 1678 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.08 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.48 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.93–2.06 (1H, m), 2.21–2.32 (1H, m), 2.42 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.49–2.62 (1H, m), 2.84–2.97 (1H, m), 3.54 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 7.17 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, ArH), 7.18 (1H, s, ArH), 7.95 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, ArH); δ_C 22.0, 23.2, 24.2, 25.7, 33.8, 34.9, 41.1, 49.1, 51.6, 127.2, 127.7, 128.4, 131.0, 143.3, 147.4, 177.2, 198.1.

4,7-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-4-(1-methyl-1-methoxycarbonyl)ethyl-1-tetralone (10b) :

Oxidation of the ester **9b** with chromic acid as described above for **10a** afforded the keto-ester **10b** as a crystalline compound in 78% yield, m.p. 97–98° (Found : C, 70.81; H, 8.04. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires : C, 71.03; H, 7.95%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1730, 1680 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.11 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.48 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.98–2.05 (1H, m), 2.21–2.28 (1H, m), 2.23 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.44–

2.57 (1H, m), 2.78–2.91 (1H, m), 3.58 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 3.90 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 6.76 (1H, s, ArH), 7.85 (1H, s, ArH); δ_{C} 15.6, 23.4, 24.3, 25.8, 34.0, 34.8, 41.4, 49.2, 51.6, 55.3, 108.4, 125.7, 126.4, 129.5, 147.7, 161.4, 177.2, 197.2.

Preparation of the lactone (11a) :

To a solution of the foregoing keto-ester (**10a**) (1.1 g, 4 mmol) in methylene chloride (10 ml) was added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (1.9 g) all at once. The suspension was cooled to 0° and trifluoroacetic acid (0.51 g, 4.41 mmol) was added dropwise over 5 min. The mixture was protected from light, stirred at room temperature for 16 h and then diluted with water and extracted with methylene chloride. The organic extract was washed successively with aqueous sodium sulfite, aqueous potassium carbonate, water till neutral and dried. The residue remaining upon evaporation of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel (25 g). Elution with ether-light petroleum (1 : 4) furnished the lactone (**11a**) (0.98 g, 84%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 70.24; H, 7.88. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 70.32; H, 7.64%); ν_{max} (film) 1760, 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.03 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.30 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.74–2.00 (3H, m), 2.15–2.27 (1H, m), 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.55 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, ArH), 6.95 (1H, s, ArH), 7.06 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 16.1, 18.0, 21.0, 21.3, 29.9, 32.2, 41.6, 45.0, 51.5, 116.1, 127.1, 127.6, 128.9, 133.7, 147.9, 173.2, 174.0.

Preparation of the lactone (11b) :

This was obtained from **10b** in 88% yield, under the same reaction conditions as above for **11a**, as a colourless oil (Found : C, 67.61; H, 7.51. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 67.48; H, 7.55%); ν_{max} (film) 1755, 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.04 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.30 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.37 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.19 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 1.72–2.27 (4H, m), 3.54 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 3.84 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 6.57 (1H, s, ArH), 6.80 (1H, s, ArH); δ_{C} 15.7, 16.4, 18.1, 21.3, 30.0, 32.4, 41.7, 45.0, 51.5, 55.8, 108.0, 118.4, 125.5, 127.0, 143.3, 154.2, 173.2, 174.2.

Dimethyl 2,2,3-trimethyl-3-(2-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)adipate (12a) :

The foregoing lactone (**11a**) (0.9 g, 3.1 mmol) was hydrolysed by refluxing under nitrogen for 3 h with 10% potassium hydroxide in methanol-water (1 : 1, 15 ml). It was then cooled to 50° and dimethyl sulfate (1.3 g) was added with stirring during 10 min. After stirring for another 5 min, 10% aqueous potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was added followed by dimethyl sulfate (0.5 g, dropwise addition) at 60°. The reaction mixture was stirred at 60° for 10 min and then at 80° for 1 h. It was then cooled and extracted with

ether to remove any neutral material present. The alkaline solution was then acidified with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted repeatedly with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and concentrated. The residue was esterified by treatment with an excess ethereal solution of diazomethane at 0°. Usual work-up of the reaction mixture followed by chromatography of the crude product over silica gel (25 g) and elution with ether-light petroleum (1 : 4) afforded the dimethyl ester (**12a**) (0.87 g, 84%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 67.96; H, 8.60. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 67.83; H, 8.39%); ν_{max} (film) 1737 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.12, 1.14 (2 \times 3H, 2s, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.43 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.70–2.22 (3H, m), 2.27 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.10–3.24 (1H, m), 3.54, 3.63 (2 \times 3H, 2s, 2 \times CO_2CH_3), 3.71 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 6.73 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH), 6.95 (1H, s, ArH), 7.00 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 20.6, 22.3, 22.3, 23.7, 30.6, 31.4, 46.7, 50.0, 51.1, 51.3, 54.7, 111.1, 128.2, 128.6, 129.4, 132.0, 156.5, 174.9, 177.0.

Dimethyl 2,2,3-trimethyl-3-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-methylphenyl)adipate (12b) :

The diester **12b** was prepared from the lactone **11b** by the above procedure for **12a** as a colourless oil in 85% yield (Found : C, 65.48; H, 8.02. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 65.55; H, 8.25%); ν_{max} (film) 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.14 (6H, s, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.43 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.73–2.19 (4H, m), 2.17 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.56, 3.63 (2 \times 3H, 2s, 2 \times CO_2CH_3), 3.69, 3.75 (2 \times 3H, 2s, 2 \times ArOCH_3), 6.63 (1H, s, ArH), 6.65 (1H, s, ArH); δ_{C} 15.8, 22.3, 22.5, 23.6, 30.7, 31.5, 47.0, 50.2, 51.3, 51.4, 55.3, 56.1, 114.4, 114.6, 126.0, 127.5, 150.9, 152.7, 174.9, 177.1.

2,2,3-Trimethyl-3-(2-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)cyclopentan-1-one (13a) :

To a stirred suspension of potassium tert-butoxide (6.25 g, 55.8 mmol) in dry thiophene free benzene (70 ml) was added under nitrogen a solution of the foregoing dimethyl ester (**12a**) (0.75 g, 2.23 mmol) in benzene (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled, acidified with 3 *N* hydrochloric acid (20 ml) and extracted with benzene. The organic extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate, water and dried. The solvent was evaporated off. The residue was taken up in distilled dimethylsulfoxide (5 ml). After the addition of sodium chloride (0.4 g) and water (0.4 ml), the mixture was stirred under nitrogen at 155° for 4 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and concentrated. Chromatography of the crude product over silica gel (20 g) and elution with ether-light petroleum (1 : 19)

furnished the cyclopentanone derivative (**13a**) (0.41 g, 75%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 77.95; H, 9.19. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires : C, 78.01; H, 9.00%); ν_{\max} (film) 1738 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 0.66 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.39 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.97–2.06 (1H, m), 2.30 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.40–2.57 (3H, m), 3.72 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 6.76 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.01 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.12 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 20.8, 21.8, 21.8, 23.4, 32.6, 34.5, 48.7, 52.6, 54.2, 111.0, 127.7, 128.6, 129.2, 134.4, 155.9, 223.2.

2,2,3-Trimethyl-3-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-methylphenyl)-cyclopentan-1-one (13b) :

This was prepared from the diester **12b** under the same reaction conditions described above for **13a**. The cyclopentanone **13b** was obtained in 72% yield as a colourless oil (Found : C, 73.81; H, 8.92. $C_{17}H_{24}O_3$ requires : C, 73.88; H, 8.75%); ν_{\max} (film) 1730 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 0.70 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.02–2.13 (1H, m), 2.21 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.41–2.53 (3H, m), 3.71 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 3.80 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 6.68 (1H, s, ArH), 6.85 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 15.7, 21.5, 21.7, 23.5, 32.5, 34.4, 48.8, 52.7, 54.8, 56.3, 111.6, 114.3, 125.3, 132.5, 151.2, 151.9, 223.0.

(±)-α-Herbertenol (1) :

A mixture of the foregoing cyclopentanone (**13a**) (0.2 g, 0.81 mmol), hydrazine hydrate (2.7 ml, 99%), hydrazine dihydrochloride (0.67 g) and diethylene glycol (8 ml) was heated to 125° under nitrogen and kept at that temperature for 2 h. It was then cooled to 70° and solid pellets of potassium hydroxide (1 g) were added. The temperature was gradually raised to 210° and maintained at 210 – 220° for 3 h. Usual work up with ether followed by chromatography of the crude product over silica gel (5 g) and elution with ether-light petroleum (1 : 9) furnished (±)-α-herbertenol methyl ether (0.15 g, 80%) as a colourless oil [δ_H 0.68, 1.14 (2 × 3H, 2s, $(CH_3)_2$), 1.35 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.44–1.74 (5H, m), 2.27 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.44–2.54 (1H, m), 3.74 (3H, s, $ArOCH_3$), 6.75 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH), 6.96 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.11 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 20.5, 20.9, 23.0, 25.9, 27.5, 39.8, 42.0, 44.1, 51.1, 54.8, 111.5, 127.0, 128.7, 129.6, 135.9, 156.6]. The methyl ether (0.15 g) was dissolved in dichloromethane (2 ml). A solution of boron tribromide (0.2 g) in dichloromethane (1 ml) was added dropwise with stirring at 0° under nitrogen. The mixture was further stirred at 0° for 3 h and at room temperature for 16 h. It was then diluted with cold water and extracted with

dichloromethane. The organic extract was washed with aqueous $NaHCO_3$, water, dried and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (5 g). Elution of the column with ether-light petroleum (1 : 9) afforded (±)-α-herbertenol **1**¹⁰ (0.13 g, 90%) as a colourless oil (Found : C, 82.46; H, 10.29. $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires : C, 82.52; H, 10.16%); δ_H 0.76, 1.18 (2 × 3H, 2s, $(CH_3)_2$), 1.41 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.54–1.80 (5H, m), 2.26 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.58–2.63 (1H, m), 4.68 (1H, bs, $ArOH$), 6.57 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz, ArH), 6.86 (1H, dd, J 7.8, 1.8 Hz, ArH), 7.10 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz, ArH); δ_C 20.3, 20.9, 22.9, 25.5, 27.0, 39.4, 41.2, 44.6, 50.9, 116.7, 127.2, 128.9, 130.0, 133.0, 152.3.

(±)-1,4-Cuparenediol (2) :

Huang-Minlon reduction of the ketone **13b** and subsequent demethylation of the crude product with boron tribromide, as described above for **1**, furnished (±)-1,4-cuparenediol (**2**) as a colourless oil in 71% yield (Found : C, 76.97; H, 9.68. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires : C, 76.88; H, 9.46%); ν_{\max} (film) 3400 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 0.76 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.16 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.47–1.77 (5H, m), 2.15 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.49–2.53 (1H, m), 4.41 (1H, bs, $ArOH$), 4.49 (1H, bs, $ArOH$), 6.46 (1H, s, ArH), 6.74 (1H, s, ArH); δ_C 15.1, 20.2, 22.8, 24.4, 26.9, 39.4, 41.0, 44.7, 50.8, 116.2, 119.1, 121.9, 132.0, 146.8, 148.1.

(±)-Cuparene-1,4-quinone (3) :

To a solution of the above diol (**2**) (0.15 g, 0.64 mmol) in 5 ml of a 3 : 1 mixture of acetonitrile and water was added ceric ammonium nitrate (1.04 g, 1.9 mmol) at 25° . A bright yellow solution was formed immediately. TLC analysis indicated that oxidation was complete. The resulting solution was quenched with 8 ml of saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate. It was then extracted with ether, washed with brine, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (5 g) using ether : light petroleum (1 : 5) as eluent to afford the quinone (**3**) (0.13 g, 88%) as pale yellow plates; m.p. 76° (Found : C, 77.41; H, 8.42. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires : C, 77.55; H, 8.68%); ν_{\max} (KBr) $2960, 1641\text{ cm}^{-1}$; δ_H 0.74 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.29 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.51–1.76 (5H, m), 2.01 (3H, d, J 1.5 Hz, $CH=C(CH_3)$), 2.20–2.29 (1H, m), 6.51 (1H, q, J 1.5 Hz, $>C=CH$), 6.64 (1H, s, $CH=C(CH_3)$); δ_C 14.8, 19.8, 22.9, 25.2, 27.7, 38.5, 41.4, 44.0, 51.3, 133.9, 135.5, 143.6, 155.0, 188.2, 188.6.

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